

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

PEST MANAGEMENT IN POTATO GROWING ON THE BASIS OF CROP ROTATION IN THE WESTERN REGION OF THE AZERBAIJAN REPUBLIC

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Abstract

Use of the integrated plant protection from the modern technologies assumes a significant importance for the agricultural plants productivity increase. Our researches were dedicated to the integrated fight measures for the soil fertility preservation, productivity growth, vermin density reduction in potato sowings of the western region. During the research the various variants of the crop rotation were tested. At this time the crop rotation scheme consisting of the potato bulbs which were stocking up from potato, cabbage, onion, root crop (radish, sugar beet and etc) in spring sowings, but leguminous (bean and etc.), vegetable (cucumber and etc.), orchard plants (water melon, melon, pumpkin and etc) in summer sowings, early plantings and previous year was tested in the fields where the potato is grown. It was determined that growing of the mean early ripening and mean late ripening potato sorts in the spring sowings, but early ripening potato sorts in the summer sowings and under western region condition and at this time use of the five-field crop rotation system are advisable. The perennial grass use is not advisable because of observing the sort structure and population density of the injurious organisms settled in the arable layer and deteriorating some physical features of the arable layer in the formed shift crop rotation depending on the sowing period (early, spring and summer). A bulky weight of the sowing layer in the field where the potato will be grown must be 0,9 - 1,2 g/cm³. One of the following materials must be applied under plants every year: 20 tons of rotted manure, or 5 tons of tree crumb one ton of ash made from the plant remnants.

Keywords: west region, crop rotation system, potato plant, integrated growing technologies

Introduction

The modern development of the human's society is closely connected with the environment problems solution. These problems are available in agriculture, too. The works are performed in different directions to meet the world population's requirements for the agricultural products (Parmesan and Yohe 2003; Vallad and Goodman 2004; Walter *et al.* 2005; Butov 2008; Abrosimova *et al.* 2014). One of such measures is productivity growth. The different pesticides and agrochemical substances are used for the purpose of productivity increase. And this causes contamination of the environment and produced crop. Every year fertilizer more than 300 million tons and pesticide more than 4 million are applied in agro-and biocenosis, this is a reason for balance disorder in biosphere (Delbare and Serradilla 2004; Kudsk 2007; Goncharov 2010).

Our researches show that the following problems exist in potato growing of the western region in Azerbaijan: 1) incorrect definition of the sowing time in vegetative material; 2) not investigating indications as wildness observed in potato bulb, anormal development and etc. by farmers; 3) Denseness of the arable layer during the various agrotechnical measures; 4) Chaotic development of the injurious organisms in agrocenosis; 5) not shooting 60-70% of the buds on the vegetative sowing material (Huseynov *et al.* 2006).

Since the 50th years of the last century these problems began to worry the mankind. The measures were performed in the different countries to prevent from the problem. The realized problems were directed against "Pesticide syndrom". The "integrated" conception was used by R.E.Smit and V.Allen for the first time in 1954

(Fedorenko and Manko 2005). They approached the integrated fight measures as together use of the biological and chemical fight methods. It is necessary to realize an application of the integrated fight measures system in a form of systemic co-ordination scheme (concerning the local condition) of the prognosis, quarantine, agrotechnical, genetical, biological, mechanical, physical and chemical control methods (Dr. Wolfgang and Ullrich 1998; Gerasimova *et al.* 2007; Sonnewald and Sonnewald 2014). Generally, the integrated fight measures - preserving and management of the factors that cause product loss including a development level of the injurious organisms to a degree of not feeling harmful impact. This system local must possess a local feature and must be improved. It is possible to co-ordinate both the fight methods and means which enter the separate fight methods in the integrated fight technology (Shelton 2004; Chulkina *et al.* 2009; Basov 2010). The measures performed in the integrated fight are connected in chain form. From this point of view the elements of the integrated growing technology must be investigated (Easterling and Ellner 2000; Govorov 2007; Afinogenova and Morozov 2011; Gorbunov 2014).

The control methods in the scheme must supplement each other besides they are "equal in rights". If any of the components isn't taken into account during the growing, an influence of other measures can become weaker. Depending on the plant development stage (vegetative sowing material, sprout development, 3,5,7 and etc. leaf stages, blossoming, bulb formation stages) these components create different configurations (quarantine-agrotechnical-genetic-physical-chemical; prognosis-quarantine-agrotechnical-genetic-

biological; agrotechnical-biological-mechanical and etc.) (Agrobiological peculiarities of the field cultures placing in crop rotation 2006; Borin and Korovina 2010).

The integrated fight measures can be divided into six stages (Goncharov *et al.* 2013; Ulyanenko *et al.* 2015):

1. Compiling of the map corresponding to the local condition (exactly indicating the calendar period that will be fulfilled in agroecosis concerning the season).

2. Preparation of the arable layer (cleaning the area from plant remnants and stone, autumn ploughing, definition of the food stuff, being co-ordinating the physical and chemical indications of the arable layer to the potato plant need, doubling tillage, harrowing of the plot, crop rotation or plants shift, revealing the sort structure of the injurious fauna settled in soil and soil pesticide application if it is necessary, organization of the protective stripes).

3. Preparation of the vegetative sowing material (durability against injurious organisms and ecological factors, high productivity, greening the potato bulbs, to pass vernalizing or ozonization, disinfection of the sowing materials and etc.).

4. Definition of the sowing time, norm and scheme (over the early, spring and summer sowings)

5. Performing seasonal growing (loosening of the interrows, filling of the bottom, regulation of the pH in irrigative water, drop watering, disinfection with the microbiological preparations by paying attention to the economic-injurious level or application of the deceptive forage).

6. Investigation of the naturally useful fauna and flora in agroecosis (increase and application of the microbial-antagonists, parasite and wild fauna which act under the local condition, planting the attractant and kayromon or frightened (repellent) plants).

A share of the fight methods was specified in the integrated fight measures system applied in the potato sowings from western region. The quarantine measures were defined 3,0 % quantitatively in the integrated fight measures system. The agrotechnical measures are mostly realized in the integrated fight measures system. This index is 55% and it shows that correct use of the agrotechnical means is one of the main and inevitable elements in the integrated fight measures system. The means including in agrotechnical method minimize injury of the injurious organisms besides creating good condition for the potato plant development. Though the biological means application possesses 6,0 % share, it assumes significance importance in the safety protection of plants ecologically. A share of the chemical fight method was determined 19% in the integrated fight measures system. It is very important to obey the following needs while using from the chemical means. 1) application of the pyrethroid pesticides having selective impact; 2) to pay attention to the economical-harmful level of the injurious organisms; 3) to take a rational number of entomophags or microbial-antagonists into consideration. Though the methods and means including in integrated fight measures system have various share quantitatively they are the same

powerful and can't substitute each other. Therefore, the co-ordinated or combined means of these methods must be rationally used in the potato plant growing.

Methods

Western region is situated in the western part of the Azerbaijan Republic and a total area of the region is equal to 546,7000 hectares. The stationary areas were selected, sowing of the vegetative material was performed in the different periods (early, spring and summer), depending on the height from sea-level (500, 700, 900 and 1400 m) to fix a sowing period of the potato plant.

Development of the plants and injurious organisms was specified depending on height, the observation-calculations were performed in connection with the development of the pests and potato plant in the stationary area. The experiments were applied in the Samukh district (Azerbaijan Scientific Research Institute of Plant Protection and Technical Crops, experimental area -69 m) and the potato sowings (Goygol, Gizilgaya) in the zones till 500 m of height from sea-level according to the method that was adopted in Academic Council of the Institute of Azerbaijan Scientific Research Institute of Plant Protection and Technical Crops to reveal the reasons of the degeneration and anormal development observed in the potato sowings at various heights (Mammadov and Khalilov 2012).

For this purpose Amiri-600 I (from the seed material of the potato sowings grown in the zones till 500 m height from sea level) and Amiri-600-II from the sowing material produced from the same seed in the Gadabay region) were used. The experiments were put two variants, four secondaries in every region. An area of each secondary was taken 250 kv.m. Amiri-600 -I sort was planted in the first variant, but Amiri-600 -II sort was planted in the second variant. The root bulbs of five plants were dug out in four secondaries over each variant (in a direction of the area diagonal in each secondary) and the bulbs in which degeneration and anormal development is observed were gathered corresponding to the versions (Huseynov 2012). According to this number a degeneration percentage of the potato bulbs was specified.

The following terms were fulfilled according to the method adopted in Academic Council of Azerbaijan Scientific Research Institute of Plant Protection to organize a scheme of the potato crop rotation: 1) a sort structure of the pests in the shifting plants mustn't be the same; 2) a need of the plants for the reserve nutrients shouldn't be the same; 3) the selected plants must be profitable for the farmers' budget. 4) the ancestral plants must possess high phytoncide feature; 5) the ancestral plants must rise the plants fertility and improve its structure; 6) gathering of the ancestral plants mustn't be at the same time.

According to the method the ancestral plants were selected corresponding to the season (early, spring and summer) the experiments consisting of two variants were performed. An area of each variant was 0,5 hectares. The potato plant under control version was laid in from the plants grown in the different zones Slavyanka village of Gadabay every year.

Analysis and discussion.

We present the consequences got from the agro-technical measures system application including in the measures system of the integrated growing technology taking into account the article volume. The crop rotation must be applied in order to preserve the soil fertility, population density decrease of the pests (settled in soil and surface) and not to assume negative farming importance by the pests. While applying the crop rotation the following factors must be taken into account (Huseynov 2012):

- 1) the sort structure of the pests in the shifting plants, diseases and weeds should be various;
- 2) the plant need for the reserve nutrients in soil mustn't be the same.
- 3) the selected plants must be profitable for the farmers' budget.
- 4) the ancestral plants must possess high phytoncide features;
- 5) the ancestral plants should possess a short vegetation period;
- 6) the ancestral plants should rise the soil fertility and improve structure;
- 7) the crop harvest of the ancestral plants mustn't be at the same time;

The potato plant is sensitive for the soil-climatic condition and crop rotation. The strong decrease of the productivity is observed while performing continuously sowing (monoculture) even in a high agro technical fund. Therefore, correct placing of the potato plant in crop rotation is very important. On the other hand the monoculture application causes mass development of the injurious organisms. During the research years the experiments about two variants and four secondaries (early, spring, summer sowings) have been applied corresponding to the sowing period for the purpose of the ancestral plants selection (Table 1, 2 and 3).

An area of each variant was taken 1000 (thousand) kv.m. The pants were shifted under the first variant, but the potato plant was used as monoculture under the second variant. In the early sowings the crop rotation system consisted of the potato plant, vegetable plants (cucumber and etc.) leguminous plants (bean and etc) and onion plants (Table 1). In the spring sowings potato, cabbage, onion root crops (radish, sugar-beet and etc) were used (Table 2). But in the summer sowings the crop rotation scheme about the potato bulbs laid in from leguminous plants(bean and etc.), vegetable (cucumber and etc), onion, orchard plants(water-melon, melon, pumpkin) and the previous and early sowings was tested (Table 3).

Table 1.

Grop rotation for the early potato plant

I field	II field	III field	IV field	V field
Potato	Leguminous (bean)	Cucumber	Potato	Onion
Leguminous (bean)	Cucumber	Potato	Onion	Potato
Cucumber	Potato	Onion	Potato	Leguminous (bean)
Potato	Onion	Potato	Leguminous (bean)	Cucumber
Onion	Potato	Leguminous (bean)	Cucumber	Potato

Table 2. Grop rotation for the spring potato plant

I field	II field	III field	IV field	V field
Potato	Cabbage	Onion	Potato	Onion
Cabbage		Potato		Potato
Onion	Potato		Potato	Cabbage
Potato		Potato	Cabbage	Onion
	Potato	Cabbage	Onion	Potato

Table 3.

Grop rotation for the summer potato plant

I field	II field	III field	IV field	V field
Leguminous (bean) + Potato	Orchard plants (water-melon, melon, pumpkin)	Onion	Cucumber +Potato	Garlic+radish
Orchard plants (water-melon, melon, pumpkin)	Onion	Cucumber +Potato	Garlic+radish	Leguminous (bean) + Potato
Onion	Cucumber +Potato	Garlic+radish	Leguminous (bean) + Potato	Orchard plants (water-melon, melon, pumpkin)
Cucumber +Potato	Garlic	Leguminous (bean) + Potato	Orchard plants (water-melon, melon, pumpkin)	Onion
Garlic+radish	Leguminous (bean) + Potato	Orchard plants (water-melon, melon, pumpkin)	Onion	Cucumber +Potato

The carried out researches showed that the crop rotation minimized the soil pests' population density besides increase of the crop rotation productivity. During the crop rotation the ancestral plants have a short vegetation period and this causes ploughing and irrigation of the arable areas for some times in the year, and the soil pests, the injurious organisms spending some development stages in soil expose to mechanical impact (touching the plow, remaining under the tractors drowning in the water) and perish (Table 4). It should

be noted that using from perennial grass in crop rotation isn't expedient. The same fields became a shelter and forage source for the injurious organisms, this rises the soil pests' population density and causes migration to the fields. On the other hand an upper part of the arable layer is watering out and lost. Besides it the technical means turn the arable layer surface into dust and winnow it by wind, this is a reason for compactness of the low layers.

Table 4.

Decrease of the pest's population density in the crop rotation scheme

Variants	Productivity, t/h	Population density of the injurious organisms spending some development stages in soil			
		wire worms	mole cricket	Colorado insect	
				pupa	imago
Early sowing	26	0.3	1.2	2,0	4,0
Control (monoculture)	8,3	0.8	4.2	5,0	9,0
Spring sowing	18	0.5	-	6,0	11,0
Control (monoculture)	7,6	0.9	-	8,0	13,0
Summer sowing	16	0.1	1.1	-	2,0
Control (monoculture)	11,3	0.6	2.6	5,0	7,0

As seen from the tables (1-3) an application of the crop rotation scheme and selection of the plants having short vegetation period, ploughing and irrigation of the arable area for some times in the year causes decrease of the population density of the potato pests. But while applying the crop rotation system the undesirable cases are observed. While using the different technical means the soil particles turn into dust form on the surface of the arable layer and are winnowed by a wind and the deeper layers compaction is observed. On the other hand irrigation by the furrows wash out the reserve nutrients and humus layer, disturb a relation between the soil particles. Therefore, optimization of the physical features possesses a great importance in provision of the potato plant with the water, nutrient and air. The arable layer is granular and it is one of the important terms in soil cultivation.

It is shown in the agro-climatic map of our map that Azerbaijan is a mountainous country. The plain, foothill and mountainous zones of the Gazakh, Aghstafa, Tovuz, Shamkir, Gadabay, Dashkasan, Goygol, Ganja, Samukh, and Goranboy are included in western region. The dark grey-brown, grey-brown, bright grey-brown, meadow-grey -brown, flood-land meadow, boggy meadow, steppe mountain grey, mountain-black, steppe mountain forest, calcareous, mountain steppe-brown, steppe mountain forest brown soil types and subtypes spread in the region. There is solonetzification and salinization in the region. From the soil sorts and variety the clayey, heavy loamy, mean loamy, light loamy, weak salinization, weak solonetzified, mean solonetzified, sandy, weak erosion, mean erosion sorts are observed. The references show that humus quantity in such soils changes by 1,2-9,4 %,

nitrogen -0,054% -0,565, phosphorus-0,07 -0,16 %, potassium 1,36 -3,5%, this is good for the potato plant development. But the potato plant productivity, potato bulbs measurement and other indices lag behind the quality and quantity indications of the product grown in the arable areas applied the organic fertilizers.

To investigate its reason, a quantity of the microelements in composition of ash, manure and peat was specified. It was known that nitrogen is 0,5%, potassium-0,6%, phosphorus -0,2% in rotted manure. These indices in the soil are correspondingly: 0,3-0,9% nitrogen, 0,03- 1,0% potassium, 0,5 -1,2 % phosphorus. Potassium in ash is on average 8,4-40%, phosphorus -2,0 -7,3 %. A quantity in soil and atmospheric air is approximately the same. It should be noted that the potato plant appropriates 120 -150 kg of nitrogen, 60 -75 kg of phosphorus, 240 -300 kg of potassium, 40 kg of calcium, 15 kg of magnesium from one hectare of arable layer during the season. All the substrates (exception nitrogen in ash) are good for the potato plant development. But during the crop harvest the potato bulbs measures are larger in manure, ash (when nitrogen is shortage) than in soil. One of the factors preventing from the potato plant development is majority or minority of the arable layer capacity. When this index is unfit for the potato plant the productivity abates. The arable layer bulky weight changes depending on soil type (60).

The experiments about five variants in the early potato sowings were applied in the Gizilgaya settlement of Goygol during the research years of 2013-2022 to specify a change of the root bulbs and development depending on the environment factors (bulky weight of

soil, porosity, aeration). Under the first variant the vegetative sowing material (Nevskiy) was planted in the arable area enriched with the combined $N_{90} P_{120} K_{60}$, under the second version in the arable layer where $N_{90} P_{120} K_{60}$ and 20 tons of rotted manure were applied, under the third variant the ash laid-in from the one ton of the burnt plant remnants calculation, the area in which 20 tons of rotted manure and $N_{90} P_{120} K_{60}$ were applied. Under the fourth variant 20 tons of rotted manure, five tons of chopped chaff or grapevine and $N_{90} P_{120} K_{60}$ were applied per hectare. But under the control version the potato bulbs were planted into the arable layer (soil) where the nutrients weren't added. The agrotechnical measures under all the variants were performed in optimal time and in the same rule. At the end of the season the measures of the potato bulbs and productivity were defined over the variants (Table 5).

The researches showed that the potato plant productivity and their bulb measures change depending

on a bulky weight of the arable layer (substrate) and aeration. Over the versions the productivity was accordingly 20; 46,8; 49; 48,3 and 16 tons hectare. There are potato bulbs with a large measure in the second, third and fourth variants. Being higher of the productivity and potato bulb measures in the second, third, fourth variants in comparison with the control prove that fitness of the bulky weight and porosity of the arable layer besides the reserve nutrients in the areas where the potato will be planted is very important. One of the important factors which will be noted is that development and productivity of the plants were higher in comparison with the other variants, though minority or absence (absence of nitrogen in ash) of the nutrients in rotted manure and ash in comparison with the mineral fertilizers and soil layer. Its reason is that the manure and ash aren't compacted during the season. The airing process and bulbs growing occur quickly in the incompact soil.

Table 5.

Influence of the bulky weight of the arable layer and aeration on potato plant productivity and root bulb measures during the season (Goygol district, Gizilgaya settlement, 2013-2022)

N/N	Variants	Sec-ond-aries	Bulky weight of the arable layer, g/cm ³	Productivity, ton	Additional-crop, ton	Bulbs parameters, cm (a measure of 100 potato bulbs on average under each variant)
1	$N_{90} P_{120} K_{60}$	4	1,2-1,3	20,0	4	16,2- 18,0
2	20 tons of rotted manure+ $N_{90} P_{120} K_{60}$	4	1,0-1,1	46,8	30,8	23,4- 34,8
3	1 ton of ash+20 tons of rotted manure+ $N_{90} P_{120} K_{60}$	4	0,9-1,0	49,0	33,0	25,0- 38,2
4	20 tons of rotted manure + 5 tons of chopped chaff (grapevine) + $N_{90} P_{120} K_{60}$	4	0,9-1,0	48,3	32,3	24,6- 37,9
5	Control	4	1,2-1,4	16,0	-	11,5- 21,2

So, the main factors influencing on gas exchange between soil layer and atmosphere are precipitations, temperature and pressure. As the soil air regime improve its physical characters, positively influence on biological action the agrotechnical measures (application of organic fertilizers, ash, chopped chaff, grapevine and etc., loosening interrows, filling the bottom) can regulate this process. This influences on normal development and constant productivity of the plants. Therefore creation of the fit air regime that is a necessary term of the soil fertility, co-ordinating the bulky weight to the plant need are important for the arable layer. We can come to such a conclusion that the potato bulb measures depends on its bulky weight, porosity, richness with organic substances and airing regime besides the arable layer fertility. The porosity in soil improves an aeration process this causes fast growing of the bulbs.

Conclusion

1. The researches show that growing the rapid-ripening potato sorts in the early or summer sowings, mean rapid-ripening and mean late-ripening potato sorts in the spring sowings is expedient. The agrocenosis in which the late-ripening potato sorts expose to the negative effect of the ecological factors, this rises a capacity of the crop loss, increases the product prime cost.

2. The plants which can complete their development for a short period must be grown in the potato crop rotation system. Especially, it is impossible to use from perennial plants, because the soil pests develop, migrate to the same areas and neighbour fields and injure them, though the productivity is higher in the arable areas where the perennial grass is grown. Rationality of using the five-field crop rotation system in the potato crop rotation system was determined crop rotation of the potato, cabbage, onion, root-crop (radish, sugar beet) in spring sowings, leguminous (bean and etc), vegetable (cucumber and etc) in summer sowings, onion, orchard plants (water melon, melon, pumpkin) and potato root bulbs. During the crop rotation or application of the plants shifting the rationality of the selected plants besides their biological, agrotechnical characters must be taken into account.

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